

Changing landscape of Indian Theatre Education: Challenges, Strategies, and Opportunities in Online Theatre Education During the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

This research paper explores the profound implications of the transition to online teaching in Indian schools during the COVID-19 pandemic, specifically focusing on theatre education. It investigates the challenges and opportunities educators encounter in adapting to virtual classrooms, emphasizing the role of innovative technologies in enhancing the virtual theatre experience. The study addresses technical obstacles affecting student learning and presents strategies to overcome disconnection in virtual theatre classrooms. It offers a comprehensive understanding of the evolving landscape of theatre education in India within the broader context of the pandemic-induced shift to online learning, highlighting the adaptable teaching strategies employed by educators and the transformative potential of technology in reshaping theatre education in the digital era. The findings contribute valuable insights to the academic discourse and offer inclusive recommendations encompassing both theory and practice for enhancing the quality of online theatre education.

Keywords: *Online Theatre Education; Covid-19 Pandemic; Resilience in education; Remote learning;*

Introduction:

The COVID-19 pandemic triggered an unprecedented transformation in the worldwide education landscape, compelling Indian schools to swiftly transition to online teaching. Historically, online education was relatively uncommon in India, with

most schools relying on traditional, in-person teaching methods. However, in response to stringent COVID-19 protocols, numerous schools temporarily shuttered their physical campuses, necessitating the adoption of online learning. This shift, driven by necessity, prompted extensive

discussions and debates within the educational community regarding the merits and limitations of online education.

Within this context, it is crucial to recognize the unique circumstances Indian schools face. Some experts cautioned against adopting online learning, emphasizing the irreplaceable value of in-person education, while others advocated for continued caution due to ongoing COVID-19 concerns. Many parents perceived online learning as a form of distance education, potentially disrupting the essential teacher-student interactions synonymous with traditional classrooms. Despite numerous objections to online classes, parents played a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of online education in India.

Despite these reservations, Indian schools eventually reopened their physical campuses after 18 months of “remote learning” . This decision reflected a broader reluctance towards online education and a preference for the traditional classroom setting. However, it also marked the emergence of hybrid teaching methods, wherein physical classroom instructions were made accessible virtually. This hybrid approach, born out of necessity, indirectly signalled a growing acceptance of virtual education in India and a willingness among educational institutions to explore new modes of instruction.

The transition to online and hybrid teaching methods presented numerous challenges, particularly in fields like theatre education, where the essence of physical presence and shared experience is deeply ingrained. Theatre educators, accustomed to utilizing physical spaces for teaching, suddenly found themselves in uncharted territory. The unique collaborative nature of theatre, characterized by group activities and live performances, demanded innovative solutions to replicate these experiences in the virtual realm.

This paper delves into the multifaceted discussions surrounding the shift to online teaching in Indian schools during the COVID-19 pandemic. It explores educators' challenges and opportunities, particularly in theatre education, where adapting to the virtual classroom poses distinctive obstacles. Additionally, this research investigates the role of innovative technologies in theatre education, highlighting how digital tools and platforms were leveraged to enhance the virtual theatre experience. Furthermore, it addresses technical challenges, their impact on students' learning experiences, and strategies employed to overcome the disconnection inherent in virtual theatre classrooms.

This paper seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the evolving landscape of theatre education in India, contextualized

within the broader shift towards online learning during the pandemic. It sheds light on the challenges educators face, their innovative strategies, and technology's role in shaping the future of theatre education in a digital age.

II. Literature Review

This literature review endeavors to fill a critical research gap by highlighting the imperative nature of technology adoption for the evolution of theatre education within Indian schools. Through a meticulous analysis of the provided dataset, this review seeks to uncover pivotal themes and challenges that underscore the significant role of technology in shaping the landscape of theatre education.

The advent of technology has facilitated distance education, including online learning (McBrien et al., 2009). The pandemic triggered an urgent transition to online learning, accentuating the paramount importance of technology in ensuring educational continuity (Chatterjee & Chakraborty, 2020). Internet technology facilitates online classes, and its utilization offers flexibility and accessibility to bridge educational gaps (Singh & Thurman, 2019). For example, Google platforms have aided teaching and learning in the virtual realm (Basilaia et al., 2020). Within online classes, effective communication relies on well-designed content, interactions between educators and learners,

prepared instructors, a sense of online community, and technological advancement (Sun & Chen, 2016). Significantly, educational institutions adopted innovative solutions for online learning during the pandemic (Jena, 2020). This unanticipated shift illuminated the transformative potential of technology, with videoconferencing tools playing a crucial role in facilitating lectures and discussions during the COVID-19 pandemic (Chatterjee & Chakraborty, 2020).

However, while the shift to online education yielded benefits, it also unearthed challenges such as technical barriers and disparities in access (Means & Neisler, 2020; Reich et al., 2020; UNESCO, 2020). Educators encountered challenges adapting to online teaching, including technical glitches and issues with online assessments (Kamal, T et al., 2021). Students from disadvantaged backgrounds confronted obstacles due to the lack of devices and reliable internet connectivity (Mishra et al., 2020). Nevertheless, educators and institutions adeptly devised strategies to surmount these challenges, encompassing meticulous planning, backup strategies, personalized attention, and interactive content creation (Song et al., 2004; Partlow & Gibbs, 2003). This transformation impelled academic institutions to prioritize enhancing educational quality and adaptability (Liguori &

Winkler, 2020). Additionally, the challenge of balancing academic commitments with personal life in online learning environments is acknowledged (Parkes et al., 2014).

Educators acknowledged the necessity of modifying their pedagogical approaches to online learning, focusing on fostering creativity, facilitating interactive experiences, and employing student-centered methodologies (Partlow & Gibbs, 2003). Successful online instruction rests upon dynamic content, interactive engagement, prepared instructors, and strategic technological utilization (Sun et al., 2016). Effective communication between educators and students, using subject-specific language, was crucial for fostering engaging online learning; these experiences were enhanced through innovative methods such as debates, experiential learning, and collaborative projects (Song et al., 2004).

Nagaraju's study, titled "Virtual Learning: Theatre in Education during COVID-19," examines how theatre practitioners responded to challenges posed by the pandemic. The study explores motivation, innovation, and online teaching themes, revealing different ways and approaches for effective virtual learning (2020). This investigation delves into the impact of COVID-19 on theatre education and proposes solutions to the obstacles linked with virtual

theatre classes. Within this context, Ali examined students' perceptions of online learning in Introduction to Drama and Theatre classes during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021 (123-133). His research encompassed three fundamental dimensions: the learning experience, class participation, and utilization of instructional materials. The study's findings elucidated an overall favorable reception of online learning and a moderate evaluation of class engagement. Ali, however, acknowledged the limitations of his study, particularly the specific sample used for analysis. He also proposed recommendations for future research, advocating for a deeper exploration of online learning readiness and academic performance, particularly within practical-oriented courses.

In contrast to the works of Ali and Nagaraju, Siva's study explores the challenges in theatre practice during the pandemic without a specific focus on school education or recommendations for online teaching (Tumu). Furthermore, Venkata's reflection on the adaptation of digital technology by theatre practitioners and educational institutes highlights their endeavors during the pandemic (Venkata). However, Venkata's work primarily emphasizes the vibrancy of virtual theatre performances during Covid-19 and does not extensively delve into the suitability of technology adaptation for online teaching. Amita Kini-Singh examines successful online

practices, especially in art education, before and after the pandemic (2020). It highlights the impact of technology on education, both enabling and limiting, while emphasizing the imminent transition to digital learning. Additionally, the paper anticipates the emergence of hybrid learning models shortly. In this study, she suggests that a possible future research undertaking could examine students' readiness to participate in online drama and theatre learning.

Within the domain of online learning, the integration of technology into theatre education plays a pivotal role. It is a vital connection that bridges conventional pedagogical methods with the requisites of the digital era. In this context, Indian educational institutions can gain invaluable insights from the extensive literature that illuminates diverse challenges, opportunities, and their corresponding teaching strategies. This comprehensive literature review highlights the pivotal role of technology in shaping the trajectory of theatre education within Indian schools. It accentuates the transformative nature of technology, sheds light on the challenges and opportunities posed during the transition to online education, and outlines strategies to enhance the quality of online instruction. By addressing these challenges and opportunities of the potential of technology, educators, and institutions

can construct engaging and compelling online theatre education experiences that effectively bridge the gap between conventional practices and the demands of the digital era.

III. Exploring Methodology, Data Collection, and Study Context in Online Theatre Education

Study Context and Participants:

The study was conducted by a theatre teacher with extensive experience in international schools, who also served as the researcher and author of this study. The data collection process included students from class 6 to class 12 across various programs, focusing on national and international curricula in Hyderabad, Telangana. The study did not specifically address the unique needs of specialized students. Within the educational context, theatre was considered both a co-curricular activity and a subject for these students. Their identities were kept confidential to uphold the privacy of the students and schools. The author collaborated with other school theatre teachers within the city to ensure a diverse range of data sources. The data collection occurred during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, incorporating personal practice data, online sources, and semi-structured interviews with various teachers.

Data Collection and Sources:

The research process involved in-depth data collection methods. Semi-structured interviews were chosen to

gather insights from teachers, where multiple interviews were conducted with all four participants, primarily in informal telephonic conversations. These interviews were recorded, transcribed, and verified for accuracy. Additionally, a thorough examination of online course material, newsletters, unit and year planners, assignments, students' process journals, blogs, and other materials authored by both the principal researcher and collaborating teachers were undertaken.

Data Validation: To ensure the credibility and authenticity of the gathered data, the author engaged in an iterative process of sharing findings and interpretations with fellow teachers, who provided valuable feedback. This approach facilitated data triangulation, as the author combined personal experiences with the classroom experiences of other teachers. This triangulation involved multiple data sources, including interviews, surveys, observations, and documents, which allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon from diverse perspectives.

Research Framing and Focus: The research was framed within a case study paradigm, highlighting a dual process that intricately intertwined teaching and learning experiences. The core focus of the study was to identify challenges and opportunities encountered by teachers and students in the context of online theatre classes.

This investigation involved reflecting on effective strategies for teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic, treating the pandemic's impact as a distinct scenario necessitating action research.

Methodology and Data Analysis: The research adopted a qualitative survey design, primarily employing semi-structured interviews to gather participants' responses. Thematic analysis was applied to explore and categorize the emergent themes within these responses. The narrative-based approach guided the investigation, aiming to comprehend the experiences within online theatre classrooms. Furthermore, the study intended to provide practical recommendations and insights into teachers' practices concerning online theatre education.

Results:

This study, rooted in the author's personal teaching experience during the COVID-19 pandemic, explores the evolution of theatre education in Indian schools. The pandemic prompted a sudden shift to online learning, initially met with skepticism due to concerns about disrupting teacher-student interactions. However, it led to the emergence of hybrid teaching methods and opportunities for innovation in theatre education.

The study reveals how theatre educators adapted pedagogical strategies for virtual classrooms, emphasizing engaging content,

personal narratives, and individual projects to sustain student engagement. While technical challenges affected group activities, educators found ways to ensure collaborative learning. To address the absence of social interaction, they incorporated well-being exercises and warm-ups, fostering students' emotional and social development.

Technology integration emerged as a central theme, with educators exploring innovative tools such as video projection, sound systems, and Google Tools to enhance the virtual theatre experience. Despite challenges like technical glitches and copyright concerns, the technology showed the potential to redefine theatre education. The study highlights the resilience and creativity of educators and students in navigating the challenges of online theatre education and fostering a sense of community in virtual classrooms.

Discussions:

1. The Shift to Online Teaching in Indian Schools during the Covid-19 Pandemic

In Indian education, online teaching was uncommon before the Covid-19 pandemic. However, during the pandemic, it gained prominence in many cities as schools adapted to this new mode. Despite some experts warning against it and advocating for continued closures due to COVID-19 concerns, most schools eventually reopened after 18 months.

Nevertheless, a reluctance toward online education persisted, partly driven by parents' perception of it as a form of distance learning that hampers teacher-student interactions, posing a challenge for online education.

During the pandemic, online learning was not seen solely as distance education, and it only partially replaced physical classrooms, even after schools reopened. This led to the adoption of hybrid teaching methods, offering virtual physical classroom experiences. This shift highlighted the growing importance of virtual education and educational institutions' willingness to explore virtual classrooms. These changes brought both opportunities and challenges, especially for theatre education.

Online and hybrid teaching introduced formidable challenges for educators and students as they navigated adapting to diverse online tools. The issue of accessibility emerged as a major hurdle, given that not everyone had access to the requisite technology. Students often required guidance and supervision to utilize these tools effectively, even among those with access. Moreover, the crucial aspect of social interaction, integral to students' holistic development, posed a considerable challenge in the online learning environment. Addressing this concern, experts such as Robert emphasized the role of parents in

fostering socialization during online learning, advocating for their active involvement in providing guidance (as noted in "Counselors Say Students May Lose Social Skills While Online Learning").

2. Adapting Teaching Strategies for the Virtual Classroom

The COVID-19 pandemic posed profound challenges for theatre education, a domain inherently reliant on live interaction. The swift integration of digital technology underscored the need to adapt to digital tools for social engagement. Theatre professionals and educators were compelled to transition to virtual environments, where interactions unfolded through digital screens—a paradigm shift that transformed theatre activities from three-dimensional settings to two-dimensional screens, unprecedented before the pandemic.

Traditionally, theatre educators heavily rely on physical spaces and face-to-face interactions to nurture creativity among their students. Transferring this dynamic to a virtual realm posed substantial challenges, particularly given the theatre's collaborative nature, often centered around group activities. Innovative solutions became imperative in this online setting, necessitating identifying and integrating suitable tools capable of recreating the depth of in-person experiences.

Guiding students through course materials while ensuring meaningful interaction required meticulous planning. The selection of engaging content tailored to the online theatre context became crucial. Additionally, clear communication of course information empowered students as they navigated the virtual classroom. Techniques such as personal story narration emerged as practical tools to invigorate the online atmosphere, fostering student engagement and participation.

To align with the virtual format, theatre educators adapted existing lesson plans through diverse presentation methods, including showcasing the work of various theatre practitioners. Cultivating independence in students' learning journey became essential, with the encouragement of projects that could be completed individually, such as playwriting, allowing students to express their creativity and commitment remotely.

Organizing group activities in online classes encountered challenges due to technical glitches that disrupted communication. Teachers needed to select activities less susceptible to disruptions, ensuring the preservation of the theatre's interactive and collaborative essence within the virtual classroom setting.

Addressing the inherent challenges in online learning became pivotal in preparing students for

virtual classes, benefiting teachers and students as they navigated the nuances of the online learning environment. Some students might choose not to use video cameras during class, necessitating the implementation of various strategies by teachers to engage them effectively.

The shift to online learning resulted in students needing more social interaction. To address this transition, including mindfulness and well-being classes became imperative. Commencing classes with warm-up exercises and concluding with mindfulness activities assisted students in connecting with their physical environment. Additionally, teachers remained cognizant of the pandemic's impact on students' confidence and stress levels, with lessons focusing on building teamwork, empathy, and shared values, thereby fortifying the emotional well-being of both educators and students.

Intricate challenges and the necessity for innovative strategies characterized the transition of theatre education to the online realm. Online learning tools served as conduits for engagement, but educators had to adeptly navigate these challenges to preserve the essence of theatre in a virtual space. Embracing adaptable techniques and creative methodologies allowed theatre educators to effectively overcome these obstacles, providing students with enriched and

meaningful learning experiences in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic.

3. Exploring Innovative Technologies in Theatre Education

Physical movement plays an integral role in theatre activities within a classroom environment. Nonetheless, the shift to virtual classes highlighted a need for more student interaction with the physical classroom. This transition challenged educators to adapt theatre activities, emphasizing classroom engagement that only relied on the part of the class being physically present in one location. This shift was a foundation for exploring innovative technology to facilitate individualized spatial engagement, enhancing the overall theatre class experience.

Online learning necessitated distinct pedagogical approaches across subjects and age groups. The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the importance of accommodating diverse learning styles and leveraging technology to bridge the gap between the Drama classroom and 21st-century learners. The pandemic also highlighted technology's pervasive influence on daily life and education, impacting students and educational systems in multifaceted ways. Integrating technology could pivot education from teacher-centered to student-centered, fostering greater engagement and outcomes.

While Western contemporary theatre embraced the digital realm,

India witnessed an emergence of digital technology in theatre practice. Incorporating elements from digital theatre into online classes infused fresh perspectives and engaged tech-savvy young theatre enthusiasts. Teaching theatre design required understanding technology's role, given its integration into modern theatre practices. Concepts like projection technology, sound reinforcement systems, and video and lighting equipment enhanced performances, offering new creative avenues. Educators could teach video mapping, sound design, and 3D set design courses, extending these offerings for a comprehensive learning experience. Video projection technology, especially video mapping, revolutionized theatre by transforming spaces and enveloping audiences in immersive experiences.

Google Tools played a vibrant role during the COVID-19 era of online classes. Google Drive facilitated the sharing of videos and performance images for feedback. Google Forms emerged as a useful communication tool, streamlining information sharing. Some students even employed Google Forms to record their classroom experiences. Assessment quiz apps and software such as Kahoot, Question Pro, Pro Profs, Quizizz, Quizlet, Socrative, iSpring Quiz Maker, Gimkit, Plickers, Formative, and Mentimeter engaged students. They assessed their understanding,

proving particularly effective for formative assessment.

Technological innovations also transformed how students learned lines. Apps converting text to voice, such as Speak It, Voice Aloud Reader, Narrator's Voice, Talk Free, T2S, Text to Speech (TTS), and Pocket, support auditory learners by aiding in memorization. These applications exemplified the potential of technology in enhancing various aspects of theatre education.

The integration of technology in theatre education opened doors to fresh possibilities while posing adaptation challenges. The transition to virtual learning prompted educators to rethink pedagogies and capitalize on digital tools for engagement and enrichment. By embracing technology, theatre educators ushered in a new era of experiential learning, redefining the boundaries of creativity and expression in theatre education.

4. Technical Challenges and Impacted Learning Experiences

Online theatre classes introduced specific technical challenges that impeded students' learning experiences. The absence of physical presence in practical theatre classes diminished the immersive nature of the theatrical experience. In virtual settings, students' actions, demonstrated through cameras, diminished clarity and posed interpretation challenges for teachers and peers. Moreover, the limited

incorporation of stagecraft and production elements in the virtual environment restricted students' exposure to these critical facets of theatre.

Technical limitations compelled teachers to rely on breakout rooms, diminishing opportunities for whole-class collaboration. Performances presented in a film-like format lacked direct interaction between actors and viewers. Distractions from home environments disrupted theatre games and activities, while limited access to props and set pieces impacted the authenticity of performances. Teachers grappled with maintaining student discipline during online theatre games and rehearsals.

Including resources in online classes gave rise to copyright-related anxieties for teachers, highlighting the importance of understanding copyright laws and fair use principles, particularly when incorporating digital materials. The shift to online platforms compelled educators to adapt theatre games designed initially for physical classrooms, often resulting in incompatibility. Additionally, the emotional connection between actors and characters weakened due to interactions with virtual images in virtual rehearsals.

Like other subjects, theatre education confronted unique challenges during the transition to online learning. The lack of preparedness, unavailability of online

materials, and connectivity issues presented significant obstacles. Theatre teachers needed help in designing relevant and applicable course content for online platforms. The shift to e-learning, driven by data and internet connectivity constraints, proved more suitable for theory-based learning rather than practical theatre work.

Effectively addressing these multifaceted challenges demanded a holistic approach encompassing technical solutions, pedagogical adjustments, and a keen understanding of students' evolving needs.

5. Overcoming Disconnection in Virtual Theatre Classrooms

Virtual classroom platforms, including video conferencing and cloud-based learning management systems, gained prominence in the realm of online education. However, transitioning from physical drama classes to virtual platforms brought forth unique challenges that educators had to address.

Traditionally, drama classes involve participants sitting in a circle and sharing reflections after activities, fostering an environment of close interaction. In the virtual setting, participants engaged through screens, creating a different dynamic. The teacher's ability to monitor participants was limited, as they could not maintain the same direct eye contact as in a physical classroom.

Few participants disconnected by switching to other tabs in their devices for social media or entertainment, hampering their full engagement with theatre activities.

In a few cases, some students shared a few online tools with their peers and teachers to enhance the virtual classroom experience. This approach fostered positive energy within online classes, establishing a community of learners. Through this approach, students developed leadership qualities and independent learning skills, thereby enriching the overall classroom experience.

Only some educators recognized the disconnection inherent in virtual classrooms and implemented strategies to combat it. In this case, individual video chats were scheduled to create a sense of personal connection. Additionally, teachers utilized students' names during virtual classes and incorporated their interests into theatre activities to foster belonging.

Visual engagement was enhanced by creating thematic backgrounds in video chats and using images and videos to communicate content effectively. Timely feedback on formative tasks was provided, and multiple tasks were assigned in diverse formats to promote varied learning experiences. Virtual group projects encouraged collaboration and teamwork.

Guest speakers were invited online to provide diverse perspectives,

and virtual events, such as monologue performances and scriptwriting competitions, celebrated student accomplishments. Reflective spaces allowed students to assess their progress, fostering self-awareness and growth. Peer teaching and short breaks with movement addressed screen time concerns.

Multimedia assignments explored software like video editing, image editing, graphic design, and set design, enhancing students' imaginative skills. Collaboration extended to parents, with regular updates through newsletters, phone conversations, and online parent-teacher conferences. Parents were also invited to observe student performances online, strengthening the partnership between educators and families.

Conclusion:

This research paper delves into the multifaceted discussions surrounding the shift to online teaching in Indian schools during the COVID-19 pandemic, with a specific focus on theatre education. It explores the challenges and opportunities faced by educators, the role of innovative technologies in enhancing the virtual theatre experience, technical obstacles encountered, and strategies to overcome disconnection in virtual theatre classrooms.

Key findings include:

1. Complex Educational Landscape: The pandemic prompted a nuanced

response in Indian education, with parents' perspectives and concerns about online learning influencing decision-making. Adopting hybrid teaching methods, combining physical and virtual instruction, suggests a growing acceptance of online education.

2. **Adaptation of Teaching Strategies:** Theatre educators displayed adaptability by emphasizing engaging content, personal narratives, and individual projects to maintain student engagement. The shift also led to the exploration of creative, student-centered pedagogical approaches.
3. **Innovative Technologies:** Educators leveraged innovative technologies, including video projection, sound systems, and Google Tools, to enrich the virtual theatre experience—this showcased technology's potential to redefine theatre education.
4. **Technical Challenges:** Technical issues like internet connectivity problems and concerns about copyright and authenticity presented obstacles to practical online theatre classes.
5. **Overcoming Disconnection:** Strategies like individual video chats, personalized engagement, thematic backgrounds, and multimedia assignments were employed to combat the disconnection inherent in virtual classrooms.

This research contributes valuable insights to the academic discourse, offering a comprehensive understanding of the evolving landscape of theatre education in India within the context of the pandemic. It highlights the resilience and adaptability of educators and students and provides practical recommendations for enhancing the quality of online theatre education. Moreover, it underscores the broader education transformation in India, emphasizing the increasing role of technology and innovation in shaping the educational landscape.

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